

"BIBLIOMETRIC AND SYSTEMATIC REVIEW ANALYSIS IN CENTRAL ASIA: RESEARCH TRENDS AND DEVELOPMENTS (2020–2024)"

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Abstract. Research trends in Central Asia are evolving rapidly, particularly in bibliometric and systematic review studies. This paper analyzes the scholarly output related to bibliometric analysis and systematic reviews published between 2020 and 2024 in Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, and Kyrgyzstan. Using a comprehensive search query in the Scopus database, we identified relevant publications that highlight key research patterns, thematic focuses, and the progression of academic contributions in the region. The study employs bibliometric analysis to examine publication trends, citation networks, and collaboration patterns among researchers and institutions. A systematic review methodology is applied to categorize the thematic areas covered by these studies, revealing dominant research fields and emerging topics. The findings indicate an increasing number of publications, reflecting a growing interest in evidence-based research approaches and the use of bibliometric tools for academic evaluations. Results demonstrate that research output in Central Asia has expanded significantly, with four leading authors from Kazakhstan, the largest number of institutions from Nazarbayev University (22 articles), four sponsors from Kazakhstan, and the most productive country is also Kazakhstan (87 articles). However, challenges such as limited access to global research networks and funding constraints persist.

Introduction. In recent years, bibliometric and systematic review analyses have gained significant traction in academic research, offering comprehensive insights into the development and impact of various scientific disciplines [1]. These methodologies are particularly useful for assessing research trends, evaluating publication patterns, and identifying knowledge gaps in specific fields [2]. Given the rapid expansion of research output in Central Asia, understanding the bibliometric landscape of systematic reviews and bibliometric analyses in Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, and Kyrgyzstan is crucial for fostering regional academic development and policy-making. Bibliometric analysis impact various subject areas, for instance irrigation and drainage [3], groundwater [4], logistics [5], agriculture mechanization [6], English for specific purpose [7]. Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, and Kyrgyzstan have been making concerted efforts to strengthen their academic and research infrastructure. Governments in these nations have launched various initiatives to improve university rankings, encourage scientific publications, and integrate their academic institutions into global research networks [8]. Despite these efforts, researchers in the region still face several challenges, including limited funding, restricted access to international research databases, and a lack of robust academic collaboration with Western institutions [9]. Bibliometric and systematic review research can play a pivotal role in identifying these gaps and guiding future research policies. Bibliometric studies analyze large datasets of academic publications using statistical and computational methods, allowing researchers to map scientific landscapes and evaluate the impact of research within specific disciplines [10]. By examining key indicators such as citation counts, publication trends, and co-authorship networks, bibliometric analysis helps measure research performance at institutional, national, and regional levels [11]. Similarly, systematic reviews synthesize existing literature on a given topic, offering a structured and comprehensive understanding of research developments [12]. When combined, these methodologies provide valuable insights into the evolution of research themes, the influence of scientific collaboration, and the dissemination of knowledge. This study aims to explore the bibliometric characteristics and trends of systematic reviews and bibliometric analyses published

between 2020 and 2024, focusing on contributions from Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, and Kyrgyzstan. By analyzing publication patterns, citation impact, and research collaboration networks, this study seeks to highlight the role of Central Asian scholars in global scientific discourse. The investigation employs a bibliometric approach using keyword-based queries in leading academic databases, ensuring a comprehensive overview of the literature within the specified timeframe. Understanding the evolution of bibliometric and systematic review research in Central Asia can provide valuable insights into the region's research priorities, academic influence, and international collaborations. Furthermore, identifying dominant themes and methodological advancements will offer recommendations for enhancing research quality and visibility. This paper contributes to the ongoing discourse on scientific progress in Central Asia by mapping the intellectual structure and impact of bibliometric and systematic review studies conducted in the region.

2. Materials and methods

In this review, our primary objective was to amass regional knowledge by scouring existing research. By employing the Scopus database, the most widely used bibliographic online database, between 2020 and 2024, we conducted a comprehensive search using the keywords "bibliometric review" and "bibliometric analysis" for all countries. Our analysis was completed in February 2025. From the 129 publications we identified worldwide, we selected a subset for further study on conducting bibliometric research. We utilized various tools to process and visualize the data, including a CSV file, Microsoft Excel 2021, RIS, VOS viewer, and Map chart, each serving a specific purpose in our analysis.

2.1. Eligibility criteria for article selection and review

For the search process, relevant information, such as keywords "bibliometric review", "bibliometric analysis", and all articles in English, were added to a spreadsheet. (TITLE-ABS-KEY (bibliometric) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (systematic AND review) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (review) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (bibliometric AND analysis)) AND (LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY , "Kazakhstan") OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY , "Uzbekistan") OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY , "Kyrgyzstan")) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2023) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2024))

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Published papers on conducting bibliometric research

An annual publication was analyzed to understand the development of conducting bibliometric research in education. The research on conducting bibliometric analysis has been published in 42 countries worldwide, with 129 papers published between 2020 and 2024. The scientific articles from five to twenty-seven in 23 years and reached the pick of seventy-eight in 2021. (See Fig.1)

Fig. 1. Annual production on conducting bibliometric research

3.2 List of top productive authors on the issue of conducting bibliometric research

Our research found that 160 authors from 42 countries conducted studies on bibliometric research from 2020 to 2024. Fig.2 displays the 10 authors who have published more than 77 papers. Among them, Tamadon, A. with 12 publications, followed by Kaliyev, A.A., and Mussin, N.M. with 11, Hajar, A., Hernández-Torrano, D., Zare, A. with 7, Ablakimova, N., Karakus, M., Zhylybekova, A. with 6, Kannazarova, Z. each with 4 research papers. Among this list of top authors, four are from Kazakhstan, and the rest researchers are from Uzbekistan, Turkey, Russia, United Kingdom, New Zealand, and Florida.

Fig. 2. List of top authors conducting bibliometric research

3.3 List of top institutions for conducting bibliometric research

Over 5 years, one hundred sixty different institutions collaborated to publish 354 papers related to conducting bibliometric research. Our analysis of the top 10 institutions' publications on bibliometric research allowed us to identify the most influential and productive institutions in this field. As indicated in Fig. 3, of these 10 institutions, seven are from Kazakhstan, two are from Uzbekistan and only one is from England. Among them, the "Nazarbayev University" occupies the top position in record rank (22 records), followed by West Kazakhstan Marat Ospanov Medical University (19 records) and the Al Farabi Kazakh National University (18 records), Nazarbayev University Graduate School of Education (17 records). In the subsequent position, Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers National Research University and Tashkent State University of Economics are ranked with 11 and 8 respectively.

Fig. 3. List of top institutions for conducting bibliometric research

3.3 List of top countries for conducting bibliometric research

The number of publications by the ten most productive countries in the field of bibliometric research between 2020 and 2024 is as follows: Kazakhstan led with 87 publications, followed by Uzbekistan with 38, Russia with 13, Iran with 11, China and the United Kingdom with 9 each, Indonesia with 8, Australia with 7, and Kyrgyzstan and Turkey with 6 each. (Fig. 4)

Fig. 4. List of top countries for conducting bibliometric research

3.7. Top funding sponsors for conducting bibliometric research

Between 2020 and 2024, thirty-three different funding sponsors collaborated in the countries to publish 76 papers on bibliometric research. Our analysis of the top 10 funding sponsors' publications on bibliometric research allowed us to identify the field's most influential and productive institutions. As indicated in Fig. 5, of these 10 funding sponsors, four were from China, two from Kazakhstan, one from Uzbekistan, one from Germany, one supported by Slovakia, and the last from the United States.

Fig. 5.

List of top funding sponsors for conducting bibliometric research

3.7. Top co-authorships and keywords for conducting bibliometric research

The keyword analysis yielded 978 keywords. After excluding general keywords with a low relevance score and those with low occurrence (by default, a minimum of 54 occurrences of a keyword was selected to strengthen the co-occurrence results), 54 items were finally identified. Each resulting keyword is represented as a node based on the total link strength, creating a network map of all keywords. Fig.6 shows the network map of the top 54 authors' keyword co-occurrence. The size of each node reflects the keyword's degree of importance. There are 54 items distributed over 6 clusters: cluster 1 (15 items), cluster 2 (15), cluster 3 (12 items), cluster 4 (7 items), cluster 5 (3), cluster 6 (2 items). The total link strength is 844, with 452 links.

Number of papers

1	E3s Web of Conferences	12
2	ACM International Conference Proceeding Series	2
3	Applied Sciences Switzerland	2
4	Buildings	2
5	International Journal of Educational Development	2
6	International Journal of Educational Research	2
7	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	2
8	Journal of Energy Storage	2
9	Journal of Infrastructure Policy and Development	2
10	Polish Journal of Management Studies	2

Conclusion. This study provides a comprehensive analysis of bibliometric and systematic review research trends in Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, and Kyrgyzstan from 2020 to 2024. The findings highlight a growing emphasis on bibliometric analysis and systematic reviews, reflecting the increasing importance of evidence-based research methodologies in Central Asia. The rise in research output indicates a positive trend in academic contributions, with notable developments in fields such as social sciences, environmental studies, and technology. Despite this progress, challenges remain, including limited integration into global research networks, insufficient funding, and barriers to international collaboration. Addressing these challenges requires strategic efforts from policymakers, academic institutions, and funding agencies to support research capacity building, enhance access to global knowledge resources, and promote interdisciplinary and cross-border collaborations. By strengthening bibliometric research methodologies and fostering stronger academic partnerships, Central Asian researchers can further improve their scholarly impact and global recognition. Future studies should focus on expanding bibliometric evaluations, exploring emerging research trends, and developing strategies to integrate Central Asian scholarship more effectively into the international research landscape. This will ultimately contribute to the region's scientific advancement and its role in global knowledge production.

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